

5. R. J. FORT and W. R. MOORE, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1966, **62**, 1112.
6. J. D. PANDEY and S. R. CHATURVEDI, *Chem. Scripta*, 1980, **15**, 172.
7. S. ZUCA and R. BORCAN, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1974, **19**, 553.
8. I. G. MORGULESCU and S. ZUCA, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1965, **10**, 129.
9. G. CUCOTTI, JACUERI and I. R. McDONALD, *Phys. Rev.*, **1976**, **13**, 426.
10. N. S. JOHN, G. OLAMENEV and E. R. VAN ARSTDALEN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **49**, 797.
11. A. P. SRIVASTAVA and S. N. DUBEY, *Curr. Sci.*, 1984, **53**, 679.
12. A. FRANKEL, *Petroleum (London)*, 1946, **9**, 27.
13. P. K. HIND, E. McLAUGHLIN and A. R. UBBELOHDE, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, **50**, 328.
14. P. R. NAIDU, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1970, **23**, 967.
15. L. GRUNBERG and A. H. NISSAM, *Nature (London)*, 1949, **164**, 799.
16. P. K. KATTI and M. K. CHAUDHURI, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1964, **9**, 1442.
17. G. J. JANZ and R. P. T. TOMKINS, *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data*, 1971, **4**, 871.
18. S. STERNBERG and V. VASILESCU, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1967, **12**, 1187.

same reaction when carried out with allyl bromide, 10-allylacridone (**2**; 35%) m.p. 129°, was obtained along with unreacted acridone (~30%).

Thioacridone when refluxed in dry acetone/potassium carbonate with propargyl bromide and allyl bromide under nitrogen atmosphere furnished 9-acridyl propynyl thioether (**3a**) and 9-acridyl allyl thioether (**3b**; 70–72%) (Scheme 1). Usually the thioethers of acridine are prepared by complementary reaction^{20, 21} of 9-chloroacridine with simple arylmercaptans or sodium salt of alkylmercaptans.

Scheme 1 Reagents: (1) RBr, acetone/K₂CO₃.

Alkylation of Acridone and Thioacridone

S. K. CHATTOPADHYAY, B. K. SEN

and

K. C. MAJUMDAR*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani,
Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 8 October 1986, accepted 22 April 1987

EXTENSIVE studies^{1–11} concerning acridone derivatives have lately been carried out mainly on account of their established therapeutic properties but most of the methods employed for their synthesis required the use of strong bases like sodamide⁹, sodium ethoxide¹⁰, powdered potassium hydroxide^{1, 11} etc. Recently, much interest has been shown on the alkylation of acridone and thioacridone using phase transfer catalysis^{12–16} and these again provide confronting reports^{12, 13, 17}.

During our studies on the alkylation of anthrone with allyl bromide and propargyl bromide¹⁸ via aromatisation of the acidic benzenoid system, we became interested in the alkylation of acridone and thioacridone using milder condition especially to find a way to avoid isomerisation of the propynyl group during alkylation¹⁸. In this note, we report the results of alkylation of thioacridone and acridone with propargyl bromide and allyl bromide in acetone/potassium carbonate, a versatile alkylation medium¹⁹.

Acridone when treated with propargyl bromide in refluxing dry acetone and anhydrous potassium carbonate for 24 h, acridone (~30%) was recovered along with a white crystalline solid (35%), m.p. 211°. It was characterised as 10-propynylacridone (**2a**) from its elemental analysis and spectral data (vide Experimental) and no isomeric ynamine was obtained. The

All melting points are uncorrected. Elemental analyses and spectral measurements were obtained from R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

10-Propynylacridone (2a): A solution of propargyl bromide (0.011 mol) in dry acetone (25 ml) was added to a mixture of acridone (0.01 mol) and potassium carbonate (2 g) in dry acetone (50 ml) and the mixture was refluxed with stirring for 24 h. The mixture was cooled, filtered and the solvent removed in vacuum. The residual mass was extracted with chloroform and the chloroform extract was washed with brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of solvent gave a crude solid which was purified by chromatography (silica gel column). Elution with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)–benzene (1 : 1) gave a white crystalline solid (**2a**; 0.80 g, 35%), m.p. 211° (Found: C, 82.2; H, 4.6. C₁₆H₁₁NO requires: C, 82.4; H, 4.7%) ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 660 (C=O), 2 130w and 3 200s cm⁻¹ (C≡CH); δ (CDCl₃, 90MHz) 2.35–2.45 (1H, t, due to C≡CH), 4.95–4.99 (2H, d due to NCH₂), 7.15–7.30 (2H, m), 7.50–7.75 (4H, m) and 8.40–8.50 (2H, m); m/z 233 (M^+ , 100%), 232, 204, 194 and 166.

10-Allylacridone (2b) was similarly prepared, (35%), m.p. 135° (lit.^{9–11} 132° prepared by using powdered KOH) (Found: C, 81.4; H, 5.4. C₁₆H₁₃NO requires: C, 81.7; H, 5.5%) ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 670, 1 590, 1 500 and 1 450 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃, 60MHz) 4.80–5.00 (2H, d), 5.20–5.50 (2H, t), 5.90–6.30 (1H, m), 7.30–8.00 (6H, m) and 8.50–8.80 (2H, m).

9-Acridyl propynyl thioether (3a): To a refluxing mixture of thioacridone (0.01 mol) and potassium carbonate (2 g) in dry acetone (50 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere was added a solution of propargyl bromide (0.011 mol) in dry acetone (25 ml) and the refluxing was continued for additional 4 h. Usual workup of the reaction

